

Harmonizing Across Cohorts: Sharing psHarmonize to Advance Collaborative Research

I could see generalist repositories becoming the default method of archiving and sharing research data. Instead of hosting on version control websites, or university websites that may not always be available, generalist repositories could take this role. I could also see repositories creating additional metadata that would cater to specific uses and fields.

John J. Stephen

Researchers: John J. Stephen¹, Padraig Carolan¹, Amy E. Krefman¹, Sanaz Sedaghat², et al

Affiliation: 1: Northwestern University,
2: University of Minnesota School of Public Health

Software shared: [NUDACC/psHarmonize: v0.3.6](#)

Related publication: Stephen, J. J., et al. (2024). "psHarmonize: Facilitating reproducible large-scale pre-statistical data harmonization and documentation in R." *Patterns* 5(8). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2024.101003>

Funding: R61NS120245 from the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke

John J. Stephen, MPH

The screenshot displays the NUDACC/psHarmonize v0.3.6 software page, which includes a file explorer view showing the package structure (R subdirectory, LICENSE, LICENSE.md, README, DESCRIPTION, NAMESPACE, and NUDACC/psHarmonize.Rproj). Below this, there is a list of recent updates and a detailed view of the package's README file. The README file contains a description of the package's purpose, installation instructions, and a list of functions available in the psHarmonize (0.3.5) package. The functions listed include: harmonization_sheet_example, create_error_log_report, range_function_list, code_modify_func, header_borders, and cohort_id. The R logo is also visible in the center of the screenshot.

Background

With the rise of pooled multi-cohort studies, harmonizing diverse datasets has become essential but remains complex and error-prone. The psHarmonize R package streamlines this process by centralizing transformation instructions in a structured “harmonization sheet,” applying consistent coding, and generating harmonized outputs in both long and wide formats. It also produces R Markdown reports for quality assurance.

Originally developed for the Dementia Risk Prediction Project (DRPP), which harmonized 43 variables across 16 cohorts and over 100,000 participants, psHarmonize has proven to be a scalable and reproducible solution for multi-study data integration.

Evolution of Data Sharing

Data sharing has become more common in research, with many teams now offering access to analytical datasets or providing request procedures. This shift supports reproducibility and allows others to validate findings or apply new models. While data was once shared mainly through supplementary materials, generalist repositories now offer easier, more reliable access—making research outputs more transparent and usable.

Challenges and Solutions

In collaborative research projects like the DRPP, a key challenge is enabling external partners to harmonize their data when direct access to the dataset is restricted.

Sharing the psHarmonize R package via Zenodo addressed this challenge by providing:

- A stable, citable platform with DOI assignment and GitHub integration, ensuring collaborators could access the most up-to-date version of the package.
- A practical tool that allowed other research teams to harmonize data across cohorts independently, even without centralized data sharing, supporting both collaboration and reproducibility.

Patterns
CoPress
OPEN ACCESS

Descriptor:
psHarmonize: Facilitating reproducible large-scale pre-statistical data harmonization and documentation in R

John J. Stephen,^{1,2*} Padraig Carrigan,¹ Amy E. Krefman,¹ Sanaz Setoohi,¹ Maxwell Mansoff,¹ Norrina B. Allen,¹ and Denise M. Scholtens,¹
¹Department of Preventive Medicine, Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine, Chicago, IL, 60611, USA
²Division of Epidemiology and Community Health, University of Minnesota School of Public Health, Minneapolis, MN 55455, USA
³Department of Medical Social Sciences, Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine, Chicago, IL, 60611, USA
 *Lead contact
 Correspondence: john.j.stephen@northwestern.edu (J.J.S.), nicole.brown@northwestern.edu (D.M.S.)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-12122-9>

Figure 1. Harmonization workflow diagram
 Pre-statistical harmonization begins with cataloging data from the datasets to be harmonized. Decisions on how to harmonize categorical and continuous data are made in collaboration with the research team. The harmonization sheet can be used to record all harmonization instructions; the harmonization sheet then serves as primary input into the harmonization function in the psHarmonize R package. Long and wide harmonized datasets are generated, and summary reports are generated for viewing results.

Impact of Data Sharing

The psHarmonize package has meaningfully expanded the reach and impact of the research. It enabled collaborators working on external validation of the DRPP model to harmonize their datasets independently, even without direct access to the original data. Beyond DRPP, the package has also been adopted in other public health research efforts, including the Collaborative Cohort of Cohorts for COVID-19 Research (C4R) Study. Its growing use is reflected in several papers currently in preparation, underscoring the package's value to the broader research community.

Looking Forward

psHarmonize provides a practical solution for harmonizing data from multiple sources, supporting scalable and reproducible analyses across studies and disciplines. Generalist repositories like Zenodo are well-positioned to become the default for sharing research outputs, offering more stable and accessible archiving. As repositories evolve, enhanced metadata, such as programming language tags, can further improve discoverability and usability for diverse research communities.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo archive page for the psHarmonize R package. It includes the SoftwareHeritage logo, a search bar, and a list of features like Search, Downloads, and Save code now. The main content area displays the package name, version (5), and release date (07 May 2025). Below this, there is a table of file sizes and a section for the 'Harmonized and raw weight values' with a bar chart. The bottom part of the image shows a 'Summary report' with a table of demographic data.

Source	Age	Education	Ethnicity	Gender	Race	Race_Ethnicity
ARC	40-49	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	50-59	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	60-69	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	70-79	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	80-89	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	90-99	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	100-109	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	110-119	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	120-129	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	130-139	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	140-149	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	150-159	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	160-169	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	170-179	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	180-189	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	190-199	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	200-209	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	210-219	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	220-229	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	230-239	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	240-249	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	250-259	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	260-269	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	270-279	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	280-289	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	290-299	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	300-309	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	310-319	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	320-329	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	330-339	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	340-349	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	350-359	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	360-369	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	370-379	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	380-389	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	390-399	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	400-409	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	410-419	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	420-429	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	430-439	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	440-449	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	450-459	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	460-469	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	470-479	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	480-489	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	490-499	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	500-509	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	510-519	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	520-529	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	530-539	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	540-549	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	550-559	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	560-569	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	570-579	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	580-589	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	590-599	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	600-609	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	610-619	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	620-629	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	630-639	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	640-649	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	650-659	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	660-669	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	670-679	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	680-689	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	690-699	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	700-709	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	710-719	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	720-729	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	730-739	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	740-749	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	750-759	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	760-769	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	770-779	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	780-789	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	790-799	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	800-809	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	810-819	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	820-829	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	830-839	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	840-849	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	850-859	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	860-869	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	870-879	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	880-889	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	890-899	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	900-909	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	910-919	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	920-929	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	930-939	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	940-949	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	950-959	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	960-969	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	970-979	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	980-989	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	990-999	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1000-1009	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1010-1019	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1020-1029	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1030-1039	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1040-1049	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1050-1059	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1060-1069	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1070-1079	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1080-1089	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1090-1099	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1100-1109	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1110-1119	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1120-1129	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1130-1139	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1140-1149	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1150-1159	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1160-1169	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1170-1179	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1180-1189	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1190-1199	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1200-1209	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1210-1219	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1220-1229	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1230-1239	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1240-1249	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1250-1259	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1260-1269	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1270-1279	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1280-1289	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1290-1299	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1300-1309	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1310-1319	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1320-1329	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1330-1339	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1340-1349	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1350-1359	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1360-1369	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1370-1379	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1380-1389	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1390-1399	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1400-1409	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1410-1419	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1420-1429	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1430-1439	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1440-1449	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1450-1459	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1460-1469	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1470-1479	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1480-1489	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1490-1499	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1500-1509	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1510-1519	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1520-1529	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1530-1539	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1540-1549	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1550-1559	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1560-1569	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1570-1579	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1580-1589	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1590-1599	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1600-1609	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1610-1619	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1620-1629	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1630-1639	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1640-1649	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1650-1659	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1660-1669	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female
ARC	1670-1679	High School	White	Female	White	White_Female

Accelerating Research Sharing and Reuse with Zenodo and GREI

Zenodo and **GREI** work collaboratively to support researchers in sharing, preserving, and reusing data across disciplines.

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed by **CERN** through the **OpenAIRE program**. For over a decade, it has enabled researchers to share, preserve, and cite diverse research outputs. Powered by **InvenioRDM**, Zenodo offers a flexible, open-source foundation that supports modern research workflows and data management best practices. **InvenioRDM** is the engine and community behind Zenodo. Learn more and connect with the InvenioRDM open source community!

The **Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)** is a collaborative effort funded by the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy to enhance access to and reuse of research data. GREI supports a network of generalist repositories like Zenodo to promote open science, data sharing, and reproducibility across disciplines.

GREI: Real-World Impact

- Funded by the **NIH Office of Data Science Strategy 10T2DB000013**
- Promotes **transparent, reproducible, and scalable** research

Learn more:

- 🖥️ Try it out! <https://inveniordm.web.cern.ch>
- 👉 InvenioRDM Software Open Source Community <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>
- 📄 Documentation <https://inveniordm.docs.cern.ch>
- 💬 Chat with us on Discord <https://discord.gg/8qatqBC>
- ✉️ Send us a message at <https://zenodo.org/support>

Stay up to date with Zenodo at <https://blog.zenodo.org/>

Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/grei/>

Zenodo GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)" through through Other Transactions Agreement (OTA) Number 10T2DB000013.